

THE LIVED EXPERIENCES OF TEACHERS USING ENGLISH AS A MEDIUM OF INSTRUCTIONS

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the lived experiences of teachers using English as a medium of instruction. It specifically explored the perceptions, challenges encountered, and benefits of using English as a medium of instruction in the classroom. This study employed a phenomenological research design. A semi-structured interview was used to gather the phenomenological data from the ten (10) purposively chosen Pangutaran National High School Main teacher participants. The 8-item open-ended interview question was modified to fit in the context of the present study and was validated by the expert. The study's findings revealed that English as a medium of instruction is defined as a way of communication. It is used to aid the teaching and learning processes. It is also revealed that teachers have encountered many challenges in a class wherein English is used to communicate. However, the study found that even though using English as a medium of instruction is very challenging, many benefits can be gained from its utilization.

Keywords: *English as Medium of Instruction, English language, Lived experiences, Perceptions, Challenges, Phenomenological research design*

INTRODUCTION

The increasing interest in English as a medium of instruction has heightened the need to study teachers' lived experiences. English as a medium of instruction is the use of the English language in all learning areas except Filipino, Araling Panlipunan, and Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao. This is following the DepEd Order No. 36. S. 2006,

"Implementing Rules and Regulations on Executive Order No. 210," stated that the English language shall be used as the primary medium of instruction in all public and private schools at the secondary level. The purpose of Executive Order No. 210 is to strengthen the use of the English Language as a Medium of Instruction in the Educational System. However, teachers need to be better equipped with using the English language or the students. Thus, it is essential to consider this when implementing the rules.

As observed, teachers need help using English as a medium of instruction. Some students need help understanding them whenever they speak English inside the classroom. The content explained in the English language may seem impractical to the student. Conversely, students find it very advantageous when their teacher uses L1 in the explanation of the content. Using English as a medium of instruction requires considerable effort from teachers and students. Therefore, both teacher and student must work together for the success of EMI in the teaching-learning process.

The notion of English as a Medium of instruction refers to the use of the English language in classroom instruction where the content of various subjects is taught and delivered in English (Khatri, 2019). Dearden (2014) defines EMI as "the use of the English language to teach academic subjects in countries or jurisdictions where the first language (L1) of the majority of the population is not English."

A study on English as a Medium of Instruction focuses on the teachers' attitudes. Khatri (2019) conducted a study entitled Teacher's Attitudes Towards English as a Medium of Instruction. This is where the current researcher adapts the instrument. The result of the study revealed that teachers at public schools were found to be aware of the basic concept of the notion of English as a Medium of Instruction. The study also showed that teachers at the secondary level have faced different challenges in adopting EMI in the classroom, such as students' weak exposure to English, mother tongue interference, inadequate school resources, and linguistic diversity in the class. Using EMI is quite arduous.

Another study, entitled English as a Medium of Instruction: A Survey on Lecturers' Attitudes, was conducted and authored by Allo et al. (2023). This study aimed to investigate the lecturers' attitudes towards English as a medium of instruction. The findings confirmed that the younger lecturers and the lecturers with a higher teaching load in English are more positive towards the increase in English as a Medium of Instruction. This study showed that individual attitudes regarding EMI are different from each other

Research Questions

Given that the authority stipulates that the English language should be used as a medium of instruction, teachers should promptly adhere to this rule. This instance aroused the curiosity of the researcher to conduct the study. Hence, this recent study aims to explore the lived experiences of teachers using English as a medium of instruction. In this study, the researcher is sought to address the following research questions:

1. What is English as a medium of instruction for teachers handling subjects using EMI?
2. What are the challenges teachers encounter when using English as a medium of instruction? And.
3. What are the benefits of using English as a medium of instruction?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed a qualitative research design, specifically the phenomenological research design, to explore the teachers' lived experiences using English as a medium of instruction in Pangutaran National High School. Creswell (2009) defined phenomenological research design as a qualitative strategy in which the researcher identifies the essence of human experiences about a phenomenon described by participants in a study. Moustakas (1994) posited that the respondents' responses should focus on the wholeness of experiences and a search for the essence of experiences. He viewed experience and behavior as an integrated and inseparable relationship of phenomenology with the person experiencing it.

Participants

The study participants were 10 teachers of Pangutaran National High School who were handling a subject that used English as a medium of instruction. Purposive sampling was used to select participants. Only those teachers who used English as a medium of instruction served as participants in the study. Purposively select means that qualitative researchers select individuals who will best help them understand the research problem and questions (Creswell, 2009).

Data Gathering Procedures

The researcher followed the proper protocol when gathering the data. The researcher also asked permission from the school principal before the conduct of the study. Then, the researcher met with the participants and discussed their participation in the study. During the discussion, the researcher reiterated that their data would be treated with utmost confidentiality. After the discussion, the researcher began with the interview. Due to the hectic schedule of some of the participants, the researcher was asked to give the participants a copy of the interview questionnaire. This made the data a combination of spoken and written interviews. Afterward, the data gathered from the participants were analyzed.

Instruments

This study utilized semi-structured interviews. Few questions are often followed by why or how questions. According to Adams (2015), as cited by Hongsa et al. (2023), semi-

structured interviews are appropriate for various tasks, especially where a further probe is needed. Moreover, semi-structured interviews help gain in-depth information from the participants and permit the researcher to gather unstructured information and investigate participants' thoughts, feelings, and beliefs regarding a specific subject (Hongsa et al., 2023). Thus, the researcher used semi-structured interviews, which included eight questions to explore the lived experiences of the teachers using English as a medium of instruction in Pangutaran National High School. This instrument was adapted from Khatri (2019) with minor revisions to fit the context of the present study. It was validated by the experts.

Limitations and Scope of the Study

This study focused on exploring the teachers' lived experiences using English as a medium of instruction. A phenomenological research design was used at Pangutaran National High School, Simbahan, Pangutaran Sulu. Semi-structured interviews were used to collect the data needed for the study. This SSI comprises Five (8) combinations of open-ended and closed-ended adapted questions. However, this study has limited to ten (10) teachers handling subjects with English as a medium. The researcher was only able to include some teachers in that school.

Data Analysis

The phenomenological data were analyzed using thematic analysis. It is defined as identifying patterns within qualitative data (Maguire & Delahunt, 2017). Braun and Clarke (2006) suggest that it is the first qualitative method to be learned as '...it provides core skills that will be useful for conducting many other kinds of analysis' (p.78). The qualitative data gathered from the interview were analyzed using semantic thematic analysis. In this manner, the themes were concluded from the explicit or surface meanings of the data. The researcher was not looking for anything beyond what a participant had said.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To explore the teacher-participant's definition of English as a medium of instruction, an open-ended question was asked to them. The question was, "What is English as a medium of instruction?" In response to this question, teacher-participants came up with different answers based on their daily English language encounters. However, about sixty percent of the participants responded with the same perspective, pointing to the English language being used in teaching-learning processes. To validate their responses to the question, careful analysis was done to develop significant data.

Regarding the definition of English as a medium of instruction, six participants shared their definitions as a way of communication, and they stressed that the English language is being used in the classroom with subject areas taught in English to give instructions and explain the lesson's content. Moreover, some participants defined

English as a medium of instruction to help enhance learners' communication skills and develop learners' critical thinking skills. On the contrary, two participants defined it as challenging to use since learners are not native speakers of the English language, which makes it difficult for them to interact or participate in the class discussion.

Based on the discussion above, though participants defined English as a medium of instruction differently, it can be concluded that the English language is used as a way of communication. This, in return, will guide the students to be proficient and effective. However, not all of them defined it positively.

According to Yessenbekova (2023), participants had a positive LI towards EMI, which is helpful for language development, although many of them encountered challenges during LP due to their low mastery of English.

On the use of English language in the classroom

To learn about using the English language in the classroom, the participants were asked: "Do you use the English language in your class? The follow-up question, "Why or why not?" justified whether they employed the English language in their class. All the participants responded yes to the question, meaning the English language is utilized in their class. The utilization of this language, based on their responses, has different purposes. One participant who is teaching Mathematics found it appropriate to use the language as it was described as a practical approach to explaining the concept in Mathematics.

Moreover, another participant highlighted that using English encourages the students to learn the language and enhance their grammar and pronunciation. However, participants contextualized the use of English in their class, mixing it with the student's first language and often having to translate the terms into their mother tongue to avoid confusion and misinterpretation. To sum up, the utilization of English language in the classroom depends on the level of students we are teaching.

Similarly, Karim et al. (2023) strongly suggest a bilingual curriculum in which instruction is delivered in both English and Bangla to impart knowledge to the students and to produce knowledgeable and skilled graduates.

On the students' reactions to using English language in the classroom

To determine the students' reactions to using the English language in the classroom, the teacher-participants were asked this question: "How do students react to you when you are using the English language in the classroom?" In response to this question, varied answers were drawn from the participants. Confusion is one of the distinguished answers given by some of the participants. Some students, especially those who came from the lower sections, found it challenging when their teachers spoke the English language. Though they appreciated it, they still felt they needed to be more relaxed and satisfied with their learning.

On the contrary, students in the pilot section are delighted to be in this class and eager to participate in class discussions as they can relate to their teacher's words. To conclude, using the English language in the classroom can sometimes be confusing to academically challenged students and attractive to more advanced students. So, the teachers must adjust their level to the students.

Teachers from Eastern Indonesia positively perceive English as a medium of instruction as they believe it could improve students' proficiency. However, some are hesitant and would rather have classes taught in a blend of their native language and English (Nur et al., 2022).

On the students' participation in the class using English as a medium of Instructions

To disclose the students' participation in the class using English as a medium of instruction. Continuing the previous question, the participants were asked, "How about the student's participation in the class using English as a medium of instruction?" Almost all the participants answered similarly. Based on their responses, most students needed to be more participative, and some of them needed to familiarize themselves with the language.

Additionally, some students need more confidence in speaking the language because they are afraid of making mistakes and anxious about being discriminated against by their classmates. Only a few students participated sufficiently in the classroom discussion. These more advanced students felt that speaking English in the classroom challenged them to improve. In summary, using English as a medium of instruction hinders the students' participation; though some students are accustomed to it, the majority became less participative.

Similarly, Lai (2023) revealed that students were inclined to produce extensive and substantial verbal output and expressed the importance of teacher-student interaction for learning the course content.

On the students' learning outcome in the class using English as a medium of instructions

This section of the paper will uncover the learning outcome of the students in the class using English as a medium of instruction. About fifty percent of participants responded that they needed improvement or were very low on it. One of the participants said that when she used purely English language in her explanation, only a few students passed the written evaluation. These students must be translated into English to comprehend the words and phrases well. Another participant concluded that most of the students needed to meet expectations. He stated that fast learners can meet the learning competencies. However, slow learners obtain only a small proportion of the learning outcome. He further concluded that only about a quarter of learning competencies exist, with approximately twenty-five percent of the learners combined from all the sections who can cope with the learning competencies. These conclude that the student's learning outcome could be more encouraging in a class using English as a medium of instruction.

In consonance, inadequate language proficiency among learners has been found to impact them in different ways, including difficulties in understanding lectures, problems communicating disciplinary content and requiring more time to complete a course (Galloway et al. 2017).

Using the English language to boost Students' confidence

This part of the paper deals with the benefits of using English. The open-ended question was used to collect the phenomenon. The question was, "How can using English language boosts students' confidence?" Most participants answered that it depends on the level of students and their persistence in enhancing their confidence in speaking the language. Accordingly, some students can boost their confidence if motivated and try to imitate their teacher.

Moreover, being familiar with and knowing enough about the language will significantly influence their confidence. Furthermore, practicing the English language in the classroom can normalize the students' anxiety. Hence, if we want to enhance our students' communication skills, we should train them to speak English confidently.

This result is supported by Miranda and Wahyudin (2023), who stated that there are factors that contribute to neither success nor failure in the process of acquiring language, which the teachers must understand if they are to assist their students in learning English more successfully. Further, teachers must provide numerous turns in communication to improve students' abilities to communicate more fluently, ask, respond to, and answer questions, and change their thoughts about topics.

On using the English language to enhance students' learning performance

In this part, the participants were asked: "Can English language enhance students' learning performance?" In response to this, participants responded differently. Despite the differences, using the English language in the classroom can enhance the student's learning performance. This was exemplified in the statements of the participants, such as using the English language helped the students express and organize their ideas, made them actively participate, developed their critical thinking skills, and served as an opportunity for the students to practice and apply their English language skills in various activities. In addition to that, one of the participants said that it is convenient. Since it would be easy for them to read, comprehend, analyze, synthesize, and evaluate the reading texts. In this regard, their learning performance is enhanced as they understand everything in the reading texts. However, one participant said that using English can only enhance learning performance if the students can understand the sentences or phrases they have read; if not, it can only discourage the students and affect their learning performance. Using the English language in the classroom will not always affect performance positively but also negatively.

Alhamami (2023) stated that using students' mother tongue is related to robust IC, leading to better cognition, positive effects, and more robust performance in the learning environment.

On using the English language to help students become globally competitive

To investigate whether using the English language can help students become globally competitive, the participants were asked to share their perceptions on this question: "How can using English language help students become globally competitive?" Mostly, they answered that it helped students become globally competitive learners. One participant stated that if the students learned to speak English effectively, they could globally communicate with other people. Considering that English is an international language, it will be easy for students to cope with everything concerning the English language. Moreover, using the English language in the classroom can develop a creative and potential student who can utilize their higher thinking skills since they have the potential to do it in English. In summary, to be globally competitive, we should train our students to speak the language, as speaking English is one of the characteristics of being a globally competitive individual.

According to Ly (2023), English is regarded as a prevalent international language. He further stated that the two main reasons Vietnamese students learn English are better job opportunities and gaining competitive advantages. Although participants experienced different emotional reactions to EMI, including frustration over teaching practices, anxiety about the quality of their learning, and pride at their accomplishment, it contributes to the role of EMI on students' well-being and graduate outcomes (Sahan & Sahan, 2023)

Conclusions

The results of this study explored the lived experiences of the teachers using English as a medium of instruction at Pangutaran National High School. Specifically, it investigated the teachers' insight, challenges encountered, and benefits of using English as a medium of instruction. The study's findings revealed that English as a medium of instruction is defined as a way of communication. It is used to aid the teaching and learning processes. It has also been revealed that teachers have encountered many challenges in a class where English is used to communicate. However, the study found that even though using English as a medium of instruction is very challenging, many benefits can be gained from its utilization.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of this study, it is recommended that.

1. The school administration should strengthen the use of English in the classroom to develop and train students to be globally competitive.
2. The teachers concerned should continue to develop student English language communication skills by utilizing the language as much as possible in class discussions and encouraging the students to be more participative.

3. The students should cooperate and work hard in developing their speaking skills. They should change their mentality about the English language.
4. Future researchers may undertake and replicate similar studies involving all English teachers in the school (main) and annex to further validate the study's results.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher informed the participants about the purpose and nature of the research. Also, the processes to be executed, the data utilization, and the benefits they might have. The participants were free to choose whether or not they would participate in the study. No names were mentioned in the study to protect the participants' privacy. In addition, the participants were not forcibly asked to answer positively, which means they could answer the interview questions based on their interpretations and feelings. Moreover, the data collected were treated confidentially, and only the researcher had access to them. The data collection and analysis were appropriate and valid, which helped the researcher complete the data needed for the research. Finally, the researcher ensured that the study's findings were exclusive and would not affect institutions.

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REFERENCES

- Adams, W. C. (2015). *Conducting Semi-structured interviews*. Handbook of practical Program evaluation, 492-505. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781119171386.ch19>
- Alhamami, M. (2023). Instructional Communication and Medium of Instruction: Content Instructors' Perspectives. *SAGE Open*, 13(2). <https://doi.org/10.1177/21582440231172713>
- Allo, M. et al., (2023). *English as a Medium of Instruction: A Survey on Lecturers' Attitudes. OCERI 2023, ASSEHR 775, pp.360-366*
- Braun, V. & Clarke, V. (2006). Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3, 77-101.
- Creswell J. (2009). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches—3rd ed.* p. cm. ISBN 978-1-4129-6556-9. United States of America
- Dearden, J. (2014). *English as a medium of instruction – a growing global phenomenon.*

- British Council 2014/E484
 DepEd Order No. 36. S. 2006 "Implementing Rules and Regulations on Executive Order No. 210
- Galloway, N., Kriukow J. & Numajiri, T. (2017). Internationalization, higher education
 Moreover, the growing demand for English: An investigation of the English medium of instruction (EMI) movement in China and Japan.
- Hongsa, N. et al., (2023). *The Effects of TikTok Application on the Improvement of EFL Students' English-Speaking Skills*. World Journal of English Language. <https://doi.org/10.5430/wjel.v13n7p77>
- Karim, A. et.al (2023). The Medium of Instruction in Bangladeshi Higher Education Institutions: Bangla, English, or Both? *Journal of Language, Identity & Education*, 22:3, 232-246, DOI: 10.1080/15348458.2020.1871353
- Khatri, K. (2019). *Teachers' Attitudes Towards English as Medium of Instruction*. *Journal of NELTA Gandaki (JoNG)*, II, 43-54 ISSN 2676-1041 (Print)
- Lai, C.-J. (2023). Teacher-student interaction for English-medium instruction (EMI) Content and Language Learning and the Effects of Implementing Multimodal Input of Classroom Interaction: University Students' Perceptions. *English Language Teaching*, Vol. 16, No. 1; 2023. <https://doi.org/10.5539/elt.v16n1p52>
- Ly, C. K. (2023). English as Global Language: An Exploration of EFL Learners' Beliefs in Vietnam. *International Journal of TESOL & Education*. Vol. 3; No. 1; 2022. <https://doi.org/0000-0002-6384-8151>
- Maguire, M. & Delahunt, B. (2017). Doing a Thematic Analysis: A Practical, Step-by-Step Guide for Learning and Teaching Scholars. *All Ireland Journals of Teaching and Learning in Higher Education (AISHE-J)*, 9(3), 335.
- Miranda, J.A. and Wahyudin, A.Y. (2023). Pre-service Teachers Strategies for Improving Students Speaking Skills. *Journal of English Language Teaching and Learning*. Vol. 4, No 1. <https://doi.org/10.33365/jeltl.v4i1.31-32>
- Moustakas, C. (1994). *Phenomenological research methods*. London Publications.
- Nur, S. et al., (2022). English a medium of instruction (MOI) in classroom activities: Teachers' Perceptions from Eastern Indonesia. *JOALL (Journal of Applied Linguistics and Literature)*, 8 (1), 59-73. <https://doi.org/10.33369/joall.v8i1.22792>
- Sahan, O., & Sahan, K. (2023). A narrative inquiry into the emotional effects of English medium of instruction, language learning, and career opportunities. *Linguistics and Education*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.linged.2023.101149>
- Yessenbekova, K. (2023). *English as a medium of instruction in Kazakhstani higher education: A Case Study*. *Current Issues in Language Planning*, 24:2, 141-159, DOI: 10.1080/14664208.2022.2043064